

Institutional Publish and Read Licence Terms

IS AGREED this day of [6 December 2024] **BETWEEN**

1. **Microbiology Society of 14-16 Meredith Street, London EC1R 0AB, UK ("the Publisher")**

and

2. **Deutsche Zentralbibliothek für Medizin (ZB MED) – Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften
Gleueler Straße 60, 50931 Cologne, represented by the Management Board ("Consortia")**

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1.1 Definitions

In this Licence, the following terms shall have the following meanings:

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'Licence Fee' means the fee for the Licence for access and use of the Licensed Material as set out in the Pricing and Ordering details released annually by the Publisher.

'Licensed Material' means the online version of each of the Publisher's journals for which the Consortia holds a current institutional subscription.

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'Licence Period' means the period from 01 January until 31 December in the calendar year during which the Institution subscribes.

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 - Eligible Corresponding Authors are affiliated with the Institution on the date of acceptance for publication; and
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 - a. Where the article is not Open Access, the Eligible Corresponding Author will be asked to sign the relevant Creative Commons licence and the article will be made retrospectively Open Access;

- b. Where the article is Open Access and a fee has been paid, the fee will be refunded.

1.3 Licence Grant

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This Licence permits the Institution for Educational Purposes only to:

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- 3.4 This Licence shall be deemed to complement and extend the rights of the Institution and Authorised Users under the Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988 and the Copyright (Visually Impaired Persons) Act 2002 and nothing in this Licence shall constitute a waiver of any statutory rights held by the Institution and Authorised Users from time to time under these Acts or any amending legislation.

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 - alter or adapt the Licensed Material, except to the extent necessary to make it perceptible on a computer screen, or as otherwise allowed under this Licence. For the avoidance of doubt, no alteration of the words or their order is allowed;
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 - use all or any part of the Licensed Material for any Commercial Use or for any purpose other than Educational Purposes; or
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3. In the event of a withdrawal of content from the platform, the Publisher shall give written notice thereof to the Institution. If the withdrawn material represents more than ten per cent (10%) of the Licensed Material, the Publisher shall make a pro rata refund of the Licence Fee to the Institution. The refund will take into account the amount of material withdrawn and the length of the Licence Period remaining.

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 - provide lists of valid IP addresses to the Publisher and update those lists regularly as agreed by the parties from time to time;
 - use all reasonable efforts to ensure that only Authorised Users are permitted access to the Licensed Material;
 - use all reasonable efforts to ensure that all Authorised Users are made aware of and undertake to abide by the terms of this Licence; and
 - use all reasonable efforts to monitor compliance with the terms of this Licence and notify the Publisher immediately and provide full particulars on becoming aware of any of the following:
 - a. any unauthorised access to or use of the Licensed Material or unauthorised use of any of Institution's password(s); or
 - b. any breach by an Authorised User of the terms of this Licence.

2. As soon as the Institution is aware of any breach of the terms of this Licence, the Institution further agrees promptly to fully investigate and initiate disciplinary procedures in accordance with the Institution's standard practice and use all reasonable effort to ensure that such activity ceases and to prevent any recurrence.
3. The Institution undertakes to the Publisher that the computer system through which the Licensed Material will be used is configured, and procedures are in place, to prohibit access to the Licensed Material by any person other than an Authorised User, that it shall inform the Authorised Users about the conditions of use of the Licensed Material, and that during the term of this Licence, the Institutions will make best efforts to bar non-permitted access and to convey appropriate use information to its Authorised Users.

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2. Any party may terminate this Licence at any time on the material breach or repeated other breaches by the other of any obligation on its part under this Licence by serving a written notice on the other identifying the nature of the breach. The termination will become effective thirty days after receipt of the written notice unless during the relevant period of thirty (30) days the defaulting party remedies the breach forthwith by written notice to the other party.
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8. Upon termination of this Licence, copies of parts of the Licensed Material made by the Institution or Authorised Users may be retained. Such copies may be used after termination of this Licence subject to the terms of this Licence, which terms shall survive any termination of this Licence.

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3. For the avoidance of doubt, the Publisher hereby acknowledges that any database rights created by Authorised Users as a result of text-mining/data-mining of the Licensed Material shall be the property of the Institution.

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1. The Publisher warrants to the Institution that the Licensed Material and all intellectual property rights therein are owned by or licensed to the Publisher and that the Licensed Material used as contemplated in this Licence does not infringe any intellectual property rights of any natural or legal person.
2. The Publisher reserves the right to change the content (including removal of a journal on ceasing to have the right to publish), presentation, user facilities or availability of parts of the Licensed Material and to make changes in any software used to make the Licensed Material available at their sole discretion. The Publisher will notify the Institution of any substantial change to the Licensed Material.

3. While the Publisher has no reason to believe that there are any inaccuracies or defects in the information contained in the Licensed Material, the Publisher makes no representation and gives no warranty express or implied with regard to the information contained in or any part of the Licensed Material including (without limitation) the fitness of such information or part for any purposes whatsoever and the Publisher accepts no liability for loss suffered or incurred by the Institution or Authorised Users as a result of their reliance on the Licensed Material.
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6. Nothing in this Licence shall make the Institution liable for breach of the terms of this Licence by any Authorised User provided that the Institution did not cause, knowingly assist or condone the continuation of such breach after becoming aware of an actual breach having occurred.
7. Except as provided for in this Licence, neither the Institution nor the Publisher will be liable to the other in contract or negligence or otherwise for:
 - any special, indirect, incidental, punitive or consequential damages;
 - loss of direct or indirect profits, business, contracts, revenue or anticipated savings; or
 - for any increased costs or expenses.
8. Any notice given to a party under or in connection with this Agreement shall be in writing and shall be delivered by hand, by email or by pre-paid first-class post or other next Working Day delivery service at its address set out below, or such other address as may be notified in accordance with this Clause:

if to the Publisher: Alex Chan

Journal and Opportunities Lead

Microbiology Society

14-16 Meredith Street

London EC1R 0AB

Email: to both a.chan@microbiologysociety.org and

journalsales@microbiologysociety.org

If to Consortia: Petra Labriga
Head, Strategic Licensing and Acquisitions
Deutsche Zentralbibliothek für Medizin (ZB MED)
-Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften,
Gleueler Straße 60, 50931 Köln
Email: konsortiallizenzen@zbmed.de
and labelled (in the subject line) as a Contract Notice

1.11 Assignment

1. Except as permitted for under this Licence, neither this Licence nor any of the rights and obligations under it may be assigned by either party without obtaining the prior written consent of the other party, such consent shall not unreasonably be withheld or delayed. In any permitted assignment, the assignor shall procure and ensure that the assignee shall assume all rights and obligations of the assignor under this Licence and agrees to be bound to all the terms of this Licence.

1.12 Governing Law and Dispute Resolution

1. This Licence shall be governed by and construed in accordance with English law and the parties irrevocably agree that any dispute arising out of or in connection with this Licence will be subject to and within the jurisdiction of the English courts.
2. The parties agree to use best efforts to resolve disputes in an informal manner, by decision of the Director of Publishing of the Publisher and the current Vice Chancellor of the Institution. Where the parties agree that a dispute arising out or in connection with this Licence would best be resolved by the decision of an expert, they will agree upon the nature of the expert required and together appoint a suitable expert by agreement.
3. Any person to whom a reference is made under this Licence shall act as expert and not as an arbitrator and his decision (which shall be given by him in writing and shall state the reasons for his decision) shall be final and binding on the parties except in the case of manifest error or fraud.
4. Each party shall provide the expert with such information and documentation as he may reasonably require for the purposes of his decision.
5. The costs of the expert shall be borne by the parties in such proportions as the expert may determine to be fair and reasonable in all circumstances or, if no determination is made by the expert, by the parties in equal proportions.

AS WITNESS the hands of the duly authorized representatives of the parties the day and year below first written

FOR THE PUBLISHER: Microbiology Society

Signatur

Name (in block capitals): ALEX CHAN

Date: 6 Dec 2024

Position/Title: Journal and Opportunities Lead

FOR THE CONSORTIA:

Signature:

Name (in block capitals): Petra Labriga

Date: 09.12.2024

Position/Title: Head, Strategic Licensing and Acquisitions

Signature:

Franziska Fischer

Name (in block capitals): _____

Date: 09.12.2024

Position / Title: Management Board

Schedule 1: OFFER / PRODUCT AND LICENCE INFORMATION

Product- and Licenceinformation

Microbiology Society Publish & Read-Konsortium 2025-2027	
Provider	Microbiology Society Negotiated by ZB MED Represented by Harrassowitz
Product type	Publish & Read - Agreement
Product-description	<p>This offer provides full reading access and unlimited open access publications in the journals of the Microbiology Society:</p> <p>Open Access journals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microbial Genomics (since 2015) • Microbiology (since 1947) <p>Platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access Microbiology (since 2019; a research platform that allows publication of replication studies, negative or invalid results, research proposals, data management plans, additions to established methods and interdisciplinary work) <p>Hybrid journals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journal of General Virology (since 1967) • Journal of Medical Microbiology (since 1968) • International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology (since 1951) <p>As a participating institution, you will receive access to all titles including the complete archive. In addition, within the framework of this agreement, there is the possibility to publish Open Access unlimited in the above mentioned journals.</p> <p>The Microbiology Society is a non-profit association of scientists interested in the world of microbes, their effects and their practical use. It is one of the largest microbiology societies in Europe with worldwide membership in universities, industry, hospitals, research institutes and schools. Its mission is</p>

	<p>to advance the understanding and impact of microbiology by connecting and supporting the research community worldwide.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable greater access to the community and therefore the potential for knowledge exchange. • Promote understanding of microbiology, advocate for the contribution of microbiology as a science and work to address global issues. <p>As a non-profit and independent publisher, this research community-led online journal publishes journals covering the spectrum of microbiology.</p>
Specialst area	Medicine, virology, microbiology
Eligible institutions	Universities, (technical) colleges, (departmental) research institutions, hospitals, clinics
Contract period	3 years (01.01.2025 – 31.12.2027)
Archive rights	Access to vintages participating in the P&R agreement remains in place even after an exit. There are no additional fees for this.
Opt- in and Opt-out options	<p>Opt-in: Annual entry is possible at the beginning of the license year.</p> <p>Opt-out: An annual exit is possible until September 30 of the calendar year.</p> <p>The contract expires automatically.</p> <p>Existing participants in the P&R agreement are free to choose between participation in the consortium or a subscription.</p>
Access rights	Institution-wide access for all users, also for remote access including mobile devices.
Invoicing	The annual invoice to the participants is issued by the provider Otto Harrassowitz GmbH & Co. KG. The invoice must be paid no later than 30 days after the invoice date.
Pricing	<p><u>The following offer is valid for entry in 2025:</u></p> <p><i>Note: All prices plus VAT. The shares are divided into 40% Publish and 60% Read.</i></p> <p>P&R customers:</p> <p>For all facilities that already have Publish & Read contracts, the following price increase applies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 2025: no price increase ➤ 2026: price increase of 3,5% ➤ 2027: price increase of 3,5%

	<p><u>Customers with current subscriptions:</u></p> <p>All institutions that have already subscribed to a journal can also participate in the P&R agreement.</p> <p>This is possible with a 6% additional payment on top of the 2024 subscription price for your journal(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 2025: Subscription price 2024 + 6% ➤ 2026: Price increase of 3,5% ➤ 2027: Price increase of 3,5% <p><u>Price for new customers (without subscription):</u></p> <p>You will be offered an easy way to get started and receive the benefits of the P&R agreement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 2025: £ 1,500 (GBP) ➤ 2026: Price increase of 3,5% ➤ 2027: Price increase of 3,5% <p><u>Additional consortium discount (from a certain number of participants):</u></p> <p>Depending on how many institutions participate, there may be a further reduction in your institution's actual contribution:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ from 15 participating institutions: 1% ➤ from 30 participating institutions: 1,5% ➤ from 45 participating institutions: 2% ➤ from 50 participating institutions: 2,5% <hr/> <p><i>Regular price increase without participation in the consortium: 4,9%</i></p>
<p>Contact of the publisher / agency</p>	<p>Alex Chan (a.chan@microbiologysociety.org) Judith Mengler (jmengler@harrassowitz.de)</p>
<p>Registration/ Feedback</p>	<p>Please inform us of your interest by 30.09.2024 by e-mail to: konsortiallizenzen@zbmed.de</p>

This offer corresponds to the current state of negotiations, subject to change.
Status: 31.07.2024

Contact for queries:

ZB MED Consortia team

ZB MED - Information Center Life Sciences
Gleueler Street 60
50931 Cologne

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INFORMATION. KNOWLEDGE. LIFE.

Schedule 2: FORM

Deutsche Zentralbibliothek für Medizin (ZB MED) - Informationszentrum Lebenswissenschaften · Gleueler Str. 60 · 50931 Köln

To the
Library Management

Cologne, the 31. Juli 2024

Declaration of accession for participation in the consortium: Microbiology Society – Publish & Read Agreement

Ladies and Gentlemen,
Dear colleagues,

Thank you for your interest in participating in our consortium with the Microbiology Society.

We would like to point out that the personal data required for the processing of the consortium will be processed in accordance with data protection regulations.

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us:

ZB MED Consortium team, Phone.: 0221-478 5609 or Phone.: 0221-478 32145

E-Mail: konsortiallizenzen@zbmed.de

**Declaration of accession for participation in the consortium:
Microbiology Society – Publish & Read Agreement**

We hereby declare our participation in the consortium in accordance with the product and license information dated 31.27.2024.

We request invoicing on the following date (please mark with a cross!):

- KW 42 – 21.10.2024
OR
- KW 45 – 06.11.2024
OR
- KW 49 – 09.12.2024

Name and address of the facility:

Represented by (full names, titles and e-mail addresses):

Name and address of the facility for invoicing (if different):
(full names, titles and e-mail addresses):

IP addresses:

Place _____ Date _____

(Signature representative)